

**JOB PERFORMANCE OF GRADUATES IN A STATE UNIVERSITY AS
EVALUATED BY THEIR EMPLOYER**

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to assess the level of job performance of graduates in a state university as evaluated by their employers in terms of communication skills, information technology literacy, work attitude, analytical and problem-solving abilities, work attitude, interpersonal skills, record keeping skills, management skills and technical skills required for the job. The researchers made use of quantitative non-experimental design to 100 respondents and used mean, independent sample T-test and one-way analysis of variance as a statistical tool. The researchers found out that the level of job performance of graduates is high. Moreover, there is no significant difference in the job performance of graduates when the employers as evaluators are grouped by their profile.

KEYWORDS:

Job Performance, State University, Graduates and Employer

INTRODUCTION

The curriculum or the mode of instruction established by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the State Universities are set in high standards as to global competence. Graduates are exposed to resilient environment to mold their ability and character. It is the goal of higher education to produce quality graduates that are adaptable to diverse environment, keen to learn new knowledge, honed skills and gain employment to apply this knowledge to elucidate problems (*Doe, 2015*). However, the issue is a lot of fresh graduates often fail to live up the expectations of the employers and switch to job seeking again. As thought, first job is the culmination of years of hard work and a start of a happy career. Graduates job expectations depends on his/her preference, nevertheless the earning, emersion to trainings and seminar as to career progression are their focus. After years of enduring the hardship of undergraduate study and personal problems such as large debts, graduates tend to feel this as a burden to carry on and need to compensate as much as possible.

Employer views graduates as leaders of the future, individuals who can climb to the top hierarchy of the company or organization, but no one starts at the tip of the pyramid, it will take years of experience, patience and hardship (*Murphy & Gawthorpe, 2013*). Most of the employers complain on lack of core skills of graduates that needed to succeed at work and for their career. Hereafter, universities need to work together with other educational institutions to adopt strategies to match the employers demand and universities contributions. (*Ranasinghe & Herath, 2011*). Also, concerns have been raised by employers regarding difficulties in finding graduates with skills required for the job (*Sannadan, 2016*).

The global field of work in today's time have changed drastically including the perception on career progression. Organizations developed strategies in employment in order to efficiently and effectively acquired

graduates who can carry their goals. These changes challenge the universities to develop and improve the quality of education that go beyond standard classroom-based knowledge (*Freudenberg, Brimble & Cameron, 2008*). In other words, academic institutions and authorities must have a linkage to explore the important factors that companies expect for the graduates to possess as to the employability and ensure that the university graduates have the skills to fulfill the market needs (*Mehrotra & Elias, 2017*).

Demographic differences of employers evoke diverse expectations towards the employee such as gender, age etc. This characteristic plays a role in viewing the performance management of the employee. Thus, it is considered fact-based factor to ensure that this will not hinder managing the employee's performance towards work. Nevertheless, a good administrative practice regardless of its demography in the area of human resource supports to enhance the employees' performance in the organization. Particularly, there is relation that exist between age and performance constituting future issues. Age has been a determining factor to the expected performance of the employee for employers if they were able to achieve certain criteria for the job. The knowledge and experience referring age identity of the employer will be a basis of judgement and contributory factor to the performance of the employee (*Gyanti, 2017*).

The focus of the study was designated only to the job performance graduates from a university and does not involve those of graduates of private colleges and institutions including the division of employers whether associated with private or government organization. This study is an urgent requirement for university's accreditation and part of the university extension on understanding the job performance of their graduates.

REVIEW ON RELATED LITERATURE

The role of performance evaluation in an organization is one of the most important means for communication. Feedbacks are essential basis for the recognition of quality performance as to the job requirement and identify the lacking and underperforming skills in order to improve them. Also, it reduces the risk and occurrence of serious problems (*Pierre, 2011*). This study was proposed by the research and accreditation division of the university in seeking improvements in the mode of instructions delivered to the students, undermining the gap between employer and university as taking essentiality to the field of work performance of graduates.

Communication Skills. Reported in the study of *Gabric and Mcfadden, 2001*, both employers and students' judgment value on general skills such as working as a team, problem solving and effective communication was significantly higher than the value of technical skills, which still plays a vital role but to a lesser degree. According to *Treadwell and Treadwell, 1999*, only 18.5 percent new hires can perform adequate communication skills without prior training engagement. Employees lack the capability of effective writing to multiple audiences and persuasive writing; this signifies to a poor written communication skill. This result was contrary to the findings of (*Sannadan, 2016*) which portray communication skills as the highest scoring attribute among job performance indicators.

Information Technology Literacy. The adaptability of graduates to information and technology put great importance in their job performance since a lot of industries abide to the global standards of technological operations such as computer software, internet and etc. Ability to locate, navigate, access, edit and save files on a computer with the use of common software programs are what computer literacy skills comprise. These skills are needed to effectively and efficiently participate in college and at work. Furthermore, whether at work, school, home or anywhere else computer literacy skills became part of our daily lives in the 21st century (*Smith et al, 2000*).

Analytical and Problem-solving Abilities. Developing the ability of critical thinking of undergraduate and postgraduate students appears to be the most essential and important goal of academic institution. Analytical individuals who can think from an abstract situation are what the labor market values as economist suggested alongside teaching them to be ethnically proper, morally solid and to have veracity. Spoon feeding doesn't help the student to think independently and rely on self-skills, teachers must allow students to explore their capabilities in order to promote critical thinking (*Taleb and Chadwick, 2016*). Small companies, large corporations and organizations around the world frequently sought analytical skills as one of the most important

attributes for young individuals to become successful. Consequently, top universities attempt to discern themselves by concentrating on developing the students' analytical skills. Yet, students struggle to develop and apply these skills in the workplace situation (*Abazov, 2019*).

Work Attitude. Behavior at work usually depends on how employees feel towards the environment of the workplace. From there, job satisfaction and commitment are the greatest potential influence in the work attitude of an employee. According to *Carr, 2017*, third of companies are disappointed with graduates who lacks resilience, cultural awareness and self-management skills which she referred as millennials generations attitude towards work, where graduates are not prepared for the real world of work and often requires ego-massaging.

Interpersonal Skills. These skills characterize one's relationship with other people that enable someone to interact effectively and harmoniously. Also, interpersonal skills allow an employee to work well in a team, solve problems, manage time, and take personal responsibility at work. Social skills or soft skills have become difficult to establish for today's youth because youth became highly focused on technological advancements such as phones, making them less socially active. Having these skills will help someone at any stage of life not only within the office nor in the classroom walls but also beyond (*Reachivy, 2016*).

Records Keeping Skills. These skills help ensure the rapid availability of information from where and when it is needed. Any organization requires to document its activities and this can only be done by records as such, it confirms and display the action taken and the result thereafter. It protects the interest of the organization, the rights of employers and clients. It also supports the organization in delivering its service in consistency and equitable ways. Records keeping is crucial to all institutions, unless managed efficiently, it is not possible to conduct business. Records consists of past data for possible future decisions without proper information the certainty of outcomes is not certain (*Tagbotor, Adzido & Agbanu, 2015*).

Management Skills. The success and failure of an organization is directly proportional to the effectiveness of the management. Future leaders must acquire certain skills in order to be effective and efficient functioning such as, management on arising conflicts between employees. Superior must serve as mediator in resolving issues to intervene and sort out differences immediately to avoid bigger problems. Strict implementation of rules and regulations to observe discipline at the workplace. Leaders must also be a good listener and interact with employees more often to motivate their commitment and make them stay longer in the organization. Being attached to the employees doesn't need extra effort, a simple celebration of birthdays and important festival would make them feel acquainted in the organization circle (*Chartered Institute for Personnel and Development, 2015*).

Technical Skills Required for the Job. Technical skills are those specific skills required for performing a specialized task, and often involve working with 'things' rather than working with people. Technical skills remain important for managers even when they perform relatively few technically specialized tasks themselves, because they enable the manager to effectively acquire, develop, organize, and control the human resources needed to accomplish organizational objectives (*Mehrotra & Elias, 2017*).

OBJECTIVES

The study aims to assess the level of job performance of graduates in a state university as evaluated by their employer in relation to communication skills, information technology literary, work attitude, analytical and problem-solving abilities, work attitude, records keeping and management skills. Also, to identify if there is a significant difference in the job performance of graduates when the employers are grouped by age and gender.

METHODOLOGY

The researchers made use of quantitative non-experimental design to 100 respondents. The following statistical tools used in the study are mean, independent sample T-test and one-way analysis of variance.

NULL HYPOTHESIS

Ho - There is no significant difference in the job performance of graduates when the employers are grouped by their profile.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of data gathered.

Disclosed in Table 1 is the level job performance of graduates and they revealed high level with the overall mean rating of 3.76. This means that the graduates have often manifested their employers the required standard. Moreover, they manifested high level on the work attitude as parameter of job performance with the mean rating of 3.98. However, the communication, analytical and problem-solving skills has the lowest mean rating of 3.61 or high level. This finding affirms to *Gabric and Mcfadden, 2001*, that the problem solving and effective communication has significantly higher value. Nevertheless, the resulting standard deviation of .50 shows homogeneity of the employer's responses on the job performance of graduates.

Table 1: Job Performance of State University Graduates

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Communication Skills	0.69	3.67	High
Information Technology Literacy	0.64	3.79	High
Analytical and Problem-Solving Abilities	0.60	3.61	High
Work Attitude	0.67	3.98	High
Inter-Personal Skills	0.61	3.84	High
Records Keeping Skills	0.65	3.82	High
Management Skills	0.55	3.70	High
Technical Skills Required for the Job	0.68	3.64	High
Overall	0.50	3.76	High

Presented in Table 2 is the significant difference in the job performance of graduates as evaluated by their employer when they are grouped by gender. The findings reveal no significant difference as shown in the t - value of .15 with the p-value of .50 which is greater than .05 level of significance, hence the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that the gender of employers is not a source of difference on the job performance of graduates. The findings did not affirm to the notion of *Gyanti (2017)* that demographic differences of employers evoke diverse expectations towards the employee.

Table 2: Table of Significance for Gender

Indicators	Male	Female	t-value	P-value	Decision on Ho
Communication Skills	3.70	3.65	0.34	0.65	Accept
Information Technology Literacy	3.73	3.84	0.84	0.28	Accept
Analytical and Problem-Solving Abilities	3.64	3.60	0.34	0.18	Accept
Work Attitude	3.99	3.98	0.13	0.49	Accept
Inter-Personal Skills	3.81	3.86	0.41	0.51	Accept
Records Keeping Skills	3.83	3.82	0.04	0.96	Accept
Management Skills	3.74	3.67	0.60	0.52	Accept
Technical Skills Required for the Job	3.57	3.70	1.01	0.19	Accept
OVERALL	3.75	3.76	0.15	0.50	Accept

Disclosed in Table 2.1 is the significant difference in the job performance of graduates as evaluated by the employer when grouped by age. The findings reveal no significant difference as shown in the F value of 1.26 with the p value .29 which is greater than .05 level of significance, hence the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that the age is not a source of difference on the job performance of graduates. The findings did not affirm to the notion of *Gyanti (2017)* that age has been noted by many researchers as having a very crucial role in determining whether an employee will be able to perform beyond or below what is expected of them.

Table 2.1: Table of Significance for Age

Indicators	below 25-35	36-45	46-55	56-65	F-value	P-value	Decision on Ho
Communication Skills	3.59	3.53	3.79	3.88	1.14	0.34	Accept
Information Technology Literacy	3.72	3.60	3.92	4.07	2.17	0.10	Accept
Analytical and Problem-Solving Abilities	3.70	3.44	3.67	3.59	1.05	0.73	Accept
Work Attitude	4.04	3.79	4.13	3.92	1.23	0.30	Accept
Inter-Personal Skills	3.87	3.70	3.94	3.79	0.72	0.55	Accept
Records Keeping Skills	3.96	3.54	3.91	3.79	2.34	0.08	Accept
Management Skills	3.75	3.60	3.71	3.73	0.39	0.76	Accept
Technical Skills Required for the Job	3.92	3.51	3.48	3.43	3.47	0.02	Reject
Overall	3.82	3.59	3.82	3.77	1.26	0.29	Accept

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings the researchers concluded that the level of job performance of graduates is high. Moreover, there is no significant difference in the job performance of graduates when the employers as evaluators are grouped by their profile. The findings did not affirm to the notion of Gyanti (2017) that demographic differences of employers evoke diverse expectations towards the employee.

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